

To Study of Phytochemistry in “Amaranthus Spinosus” Plant for Human Health

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Abstract

The history of medicine obtained by plants to remedy is very ancient The use of plants as a source of medicines & human sustenance has been drogue since antiquity. Ancient Indian literature like a Rigveda, Atharvaveda, Upnishad, Mahabharata and Puran include medicinal plants used for drugs, assence, worships, food, fuels, poison, agriculture tools and other purposes.

Vedic literature followed by the writing of "Charaka" and Sushruta samhita, described the use of about 1200 plants drugs. The apic Ramayana has reference to sanjivani, sandhankaarni, etc.

Study of plants to search their bioactive components is of great importance in a subcontinent like India, as a major segment of population depends upon the herbal system of medicines. Herbal system of medicine is the oldest form of therapy practiced by mankind based on a highly developed instinct People are aware to use plants as a traditional medicine for the treatment of common diseases. The traditional system is also practiced in Muslim communities in South Asia. A variety of medicines of herbal & mineral origin are used.

Keywords

Medicines, Bioactive, Treatment, Communities.

Introduction

Kingdom:	Plantae
Division:	Magnoliophyta
Class:	Magnoliopsida
Order:	Caryophyllales
Family:	Amaranthaceae
Genus:	<i>Amaranthus</i>
Species:	<i>A. spinosus</i>
Binomial name:	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.

Amaranthus spinosus L. usually called "spiny amaranth" or "pig weed" is believed to originate from lowland tropical south and central America and also found throughout India.

The word amaranthus came from the Greek word "Amarantos" which means "unfading" and spinosus means "spiny"^[1] This plant belongs to family Amaranthaceae Taxonomically this family represents 160 genera and 2,400 species.

The family Amaranthaceae having an important genus "Amaranthus" a herb, which include more than 60 species, provide a wide range of food source and medicinally active components. Some of the medicinally important species of the genus amaranthus are as follow, *A.blitus*, *A.caudatus*, *A.dubious*, *A.edulis*, *A.hibridus*, *A.hypochodriacus*; *A.retroflexus* and *A.viridus*. A *viridus* can be used as a substitute for *A. spinosus* but *A. viridus* has no spines

Vernacular Names

Hindi	Katailichaulai
English	spiny amaranth, Thorny amaranth
French	Amarante epineuse, epinard Malabar
Portugese	Amaranto, bredo banlude
Nepal	Banlude11

Amaranthus spinosus is found world's noxious weed^[2] highly responsible for reduction of crop yield. Plant A. spinosus is used as a traditionaly medicine to treat diabetes^[3]. The seeds are used as a poultice for broken bones Internally used in treatment of internal bleeding, diarrhea^[4] and excessive menstruation. The root is known as effective diuretic, the decoction of root is used to treat genorrhoea and is also applied as an emmenagogue tind antipyretic Specially roots are used for toothaches.^[5] Traditionally boiled leaves and roots of A spinosus are given to children as laxative. Some tribes in India apply A spinosus Leaves are used for gastroenteritis, gall bladder inflammation, absesses, colic menorrhagia, arthritis and specially used for treatment of snakebites^[6] hemorrhoids. The plant ash in a solution is used to wash sores, the ash of burnt 4. spinosus plant is used as a tenderizer in cooking, ash also used as vegetable salt and snuff. The plant sap are used as an eye wash to treat ophthalmia and convulsions. Whole plant is used as a laxative.^[7]

During the rainy season which is also malaria endemic season, A. spinosus bark decoction is taken in a volume of about one litre three times a day to ward off malaria.^[8]

Plant A spinosus is an annual or perennial herb up to 100-130cm tall, much branched varying colour green-purple, stem 30-60cm in height, spines hard straight, leaves 3-7-10cm long, flower found throughout the year and seeds are black and shining.

Objective of study

The purpose of study is to search their bioactive components which is use for betterment of human health.

Review of Literature

A survey of literature revealed isolation of tannins, flavonoids, flavonols, flavonol glycosides, steroids, saponins, glycosides, phenolic compounds, glycolipids, volatile oil, polysaccharides and vitamins from its fruits, leaves^[9,10] stem bark^[11,12], aerial part^[13,14], roots^[15] and seeds^[16] Phytochemically limited studies reporting isolation of sterols and other compounds from the roots of the plant are available. Hence the present work dealing with the isolation and characterization of constituents from pet-ether fraction of ethanolic extract of the roots has been undertaken.

Methodology**Phytochemical analysis****Qualitative Phytochemical Analysis of Plant extracts:**

Phytochemical examinations were carried out for the ethanolic extract by a standard protocol.^[17]

Tannins:

0.5g of the extract was dissolved in 2ml of ethanol in a bioling test tube and boiled with 3ml of distilled water and then filtered. Few drops of 0.1% of ferric chloride was mixed well and allowed to stand for some time and observed for brownish green or blue black colour formation.

Phenols:

0.5g of the extract was dissolved in 2ml of ethanol in a test tube and added with water. To this 2ml of ferric chloride was added and observed for the formation of green or blue colour.

Analysis**Carbohydrates (Molisch's Test):**

0.5g of the extract was dissolved in 2ml of ethanol in a test tube and added with 1ml of distilled water and filtered. To this solution, 2 to 3 drops of a-naphthol was added. To this about 1ml of conc. Sulphuric acid was added along the sides of inclined test tube so as to form two layers and observed for the formation of violet coloured ring at the interface for the presence of carbohydrates.

Alkaloids:

Extract was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and filtered filtrate treated with Wagner's reagent (Iodine in Potassium Iodide). Formation of brown/reddish precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

Saponins:

0.5 gm. of extract was shaken with 2 ml of water. If foam produced persists for ten minutes it indicates the presence of saponins.

Glycosides:

Extract was hydrolysed with dil. HCl, and then subjected to test for glycosides.

Modified Borntrager's Test:

Extracts was treated with Ferric Chloride solution and immersed in boiling water for about 5 minutes. The mixture was cooled and extracted with equal volumes of benzene. The benzene layer was separated and treated with ammonia solution. Formation of rose-pink colour in the ammonical layer indicates the presence glycosides.

Aminoacids (Ninhydrin Test):

To the extract, 0.25% w/v ninhydrin reagent was added and boiled for few minutes. Formation of blue colour indicates the presence of amino acids.

Result and Discussion

The qualitative analysis revealed the presence of tannins, phenols, carbohydrates, alkaloids, saponins, glycosides and aminoacids as shown in table:

Table: 1, Phytochemical constituents of roots of *Amaranthus spinosus L.*

Phytochemical constituent	Root bark extract
Tannins	Present
Phenols	Present
Carbohydrates	Present
Alkaloids	Present
Saponins	Present
Glycosides	Present
Aminoacids	Present

Isolation and characterization of chemical constituents

The shade dried roots of *Amaranthus spinosus L.* was coarsely powdered and extracted with ethanol. The ethanolic extract after concentration under reduced pressure was fractionated with solvents of increasing polarity viz. pet. ether, benzene and ethyl acetate. As the pet, ether and benzene fractions exhibited same TLC profile, they were mixed and column chromatographed over silica gel. The TLC profile of various fractions collected after elution with solvents of increased polarity on observation revealed that a minimum of 8-10 compounds were present in the above mixed fractions. The three compounds isolated from these fractions are:

Compound	Melting point
A (Glycoside)	178-180 °C
B (Unidentified)	140-142 °C
C (Sterol)	168-169°C

Characterization of Compound A:

Compound A, m.p.178-180°C was found to be homogeneous in TLC and showed positive Molisch's test. Therefore the compound was tentatively characterized as a glycoside. Its IR NMR and Mass spectral studies are in progress.

Characterization of compound B:

Compound B, m.p., 140-142°C gave a single spot in TLC. It appeared as white long thin crystals, but we were not able to identify it. Its IR NMR and Mass spectral studies are in progress.

Characterization of compound C:

Compound C m.p. 168-169°C was found to be homogeneous in TLC. It appeared white solid and gave positive tests for sterols (Lieberman Burchard test) and hence was characterized as sterol. Its IR NMR and Mass spectral studies are in progress.

Conclusion

Phytochemical are non reactive plant chemicals that have protective or disease preventive properties without any side effects (health hazards) on the human body. Most of the vegetarian food contain phytochemicals except few of them, for eg Lycopene in tomatoes, isoflavones in soy etc. Some possible action of phytochemicals may be as an antioxidant, hormonal action, stimulation of enzymes, interference with DNA replication, antibacterial effect and preventing the adhesion of pathogens.

Looking into the health hazard caused due to side effects of synthetic drugs, active ingredients have been isolated from the herbal preparations and included in modern medicine. Development of sophisticated separation techniques and those of modern spectrometers have simplified new isolations and identification of active components from a complex mixture of organic compounds respectively.

Keeping in view the achievements made by earlier workers, present work has been designed to isolate and characterize active phytochemicals from the roots of *Amaranthus spinosus*.

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